

Euscorpium

Occasional Publications in Scorpiology

Scorpiops reini sp. n. from Yunnan, China
(Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae)

Victoria Tang

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Scorpiops reini sp. n. from Yunnan, China (Scorpiones: Scorpiopidae)

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Summary

Scorpiops reini sp. n. is described from Yingjiang County (Dehong Prefecture, Yunnan Province) based on an adult pair. It can be readily discriminated from all of its congeneric geographic neighbors in Yunnan, namely *S. jendeki* Kovařík, 1994, *S. shidian* (Zhu et al., 2005), *S. tongtongi* Tang, 2022, and *S. zhangshuyuani* (Ythier, 2019). Within Yunnan, it resembles *S. validus* (Di et al., 2010) and *S. yangi* (Zhu et al., 2007) most, but can be identified by its large median ocelli (relative to the width of ocular subislet), pedipalp chelal finger morphology and pectinal tooth count. Beyond Yunnan, it shows the highest similarity with *S. beccaloniae* (Kovařík, 2005), from which it distinguishes itself mainly by a different chelal morphology (weaker finger lobe and notch, longer and narrower manus with chelal carinae composed of smaller and denser granules). The validity of this new species is supported molecularly (to be published). The ocular islets are reviewed for all Yunnan *Scorpiops*.

Introduction

The Yunnan *Scorpiops* species were first reviewed by Di et al. (2011) and later by Tang (2022b, 2022c). Most described species were found near the Chinese border with Myanmar, Laos and Vietnam, suggesting that some Chinese species may not be endemic and more species may be found in the central region of Yunnan or even in the adjacent province, Guangxi. The first *Scorpiops* species described from Yunnan Province was *S. jendeki* Kovařík, 1994, followed by (in sequence of collection and publication date) *S. shidian* (Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005), *S. vachoni* (Zhu, Qi & Lourenço, 2005), *S. yangi* (Zhu, Zhang & Lourenço, 2007), *S. xui* (Sun & Zhu, 2010), *S. validus* (Di, Cao, Wu & Li, 2010), *S. puerensis* (Di, Wu, Cao, Xiao & Li, 2010), *S. zhangshuyuani* (Ythier, 2019), *S. tongtongi* Tang, 2022, and *S. lowei* Tang, 2022. Notably, *S. lowei* represents an erroneous record of *S. kubani* (Kovařík, 2004) in Menghai County (Tang, 2022c). In the same study, Tang (*op. cit.*) reported three unidentified populations from Jinghong City, Menglun Township, and Wangtianshu (in Mengla County). While the single female from Wangtianshu was assumed to be *S. vachoni* (*op. cit.*: 19), a species distributed in proximity, the other two populations could not be confidently identified based on the external morphology alone. Specifically, both populations exhibited intermediate morphological variations between *S. lowei* from the west and *S. vachoni* from the southeast (*op. cit.*: figs. 85–89), indicating potential character gradients during a recent dispersal process. The populations from Jinghong and Menglun differed most significantly from *S. lowei* in their female PTC where a count of 6 teeth was more common in *S. lowei* (12/20; 8/20

reached 7 teeth), in contrast to the 7 teeth counted in those two populations (32/38). More importantly, 6/38 pectines of the two populations were recorded with 8 teeth, a number unprecedented in any examined female *S. lowei*. Those two populations were also recorded with a higher count of MD and IAD, as well as PVTC (*op. cit.*: table 2). This general trend in these meristics led the author to speculate that they were closer to *S. vachoni* than to *S. lowei* (*op. cit.*: 20).

In the present study, a new species, *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., is described from Yingjiang County, Dehong Prefecture, based on a pair of adult specimens. This species differs clearly from all its congeneric geographic neighbors in Yunnan while resembles two most distant congeners within the province. It also shows similarity to the only *Scorpiops* species, *S. beccaloniae* (Kovařík, 2005), described from northern Myanmar, a region adjacent with its locality. In a subsequent work on this genus, the taxonomic status of several Tibetan congeners will be examined, alongside a phylogenetic study of all Yunnan *Scorpiops*, which will clarify the identities of the three populations in Xishuangbanna Prefecture mentioned earlier.

Methods, Material & Abbreviations

Morphology. Nomenclature and measurements follow Tang (2023) and Tang et al. (2024). All comparisons (except for meristics, with “/” separating left and right counts) were based on adult specimens. Pedipalp patella external trichobothrium count is expressed in *et-est-em-esb-eb* and pedipalp movable finger dentition count is expressed in OD-MD-IAD-ID. Due to the poor condition of the type specimens of *S. reini* sp.

Figures 1–4. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male (1–2) and paratype female (3–4), habitus in dorsal (1, 3) and ventral (2, 4) views, under white light. Scale bar = 10 mm.

n., the tergites could not be fully extended, resulting in a lower total length recorded. In addition, the metasoma was curved and moderately desiccated in both sexes, preventing the provision of standard three-view (dorsal, ventral, lateral) illustrations. The rigidity of the specimens also hindered a clear examination of the chelicerae, which in previous studies by the author were typically dissected and opened for detailed photography. Finger dentition color markings: inner accessory denticles = yellow, median denticles = green, inner denticles = blue, outer denticles = red. Maps were generated in QGIS (ver. 3.32.3), using ‘Bing Maps Satellite Imagery’ as the layer map. Administrative division vector layers were downloaded from Natural Earth (www.naturalearthdata.com/).

Materials. Type specimens of *S. reini* sp. n. (an adult pair) were obtained by a friend of the author, Tongtong, who had purchased them from a local collector in Yingjiang County, Dehong Prefecture, Yunnan Province. Unfortunately, the collector could not be contacted since then. The adult pair were reared by Tongtong and died due to lack of care. When their death was noticed, the adult specimens were moderately decomposed and were then preserved in 75% ethanol before being sent to the author. The adult female had given birth to a brood of offspring prior to its demise which also died out of dehydration. The offspring were then preserved in 99% ethanol and sent to Charles University, Czech Republic for DNA sequencing. Materials of Yunnan *Scorpiops* species for

Dimensions (mm)		<i>Scorpiops reini</i> sp. n.	
		♂ (HT)	♀ (PT)
Carapace	L / W	9.63 / 9.57	8.41 / 8.51
Mesosoma	L	ca. 13.59	ca. 14.13
Tergite VII	L / W	ca. 3.46 / 6.64	ca. 3.39 / 6.17
Metasoma + telson	L	31.7	25.68
Segment I	L / W / D	3.08 / 3.45 / 3.05	2.53 / 3.11 / 2.49
Segment II	L / W / D	3.21 / 3.24 / 2.54	2.78 / 2.79 / 2.5
Segment III	L / W / D	3.66 / 2.95 / 2.66	2.95 / 2.62 / 2.31
Segment IV	L / W / D	4.32 / 2.83 / 2.74	3.57 / 2.41 / 2.29
Segment V	L / W / D	7.8 / 2.68 / 2.85	6.51 / 2.18 / 2.33
Telson	L / W / D	9.63 / 2.81 / 2.9	7.34 / 2.25 / 2.14
Pedipalp	L	40.98	31.47
Femur	L / W	10.99 / 3.87	8.09 / 3.15
Patella	L / W	9.18 / 4.01	7.14 / 3.22
Chela	L	20.81	16.24
Manus	L / W / D	13.12 / 5.69 / 4.72	9.76 / 5.09 / 3.97
Fixed Finger	L	7.69	6.48
Movable finger	L	10.01	8.45
Total	L	ca. 54.92	ca. 48.22
Pectinal tooth count	Left / Right	10 / 9	8 / 8

Table 1. Measurements of *Scorpiops reini* sp. n. Abbreviations: holotype (HT), paratype (PT), length (L), width (W, in carapace it corresponds to posterior width), depth (D). Pedipalp length excludes trochanter length; patella width excludes apophysis length; aculeus of paratype female apically broken.

morphological comparison were the same as those examined in Tang (2022b, 2022c, 2023) which all had been preserved in 75% ethanol, except for some new specimens (will be detailed in a subsequent study). Exemplar photos of live *S. shidian* pair (Figs. 73–74) were based on those new materials. Photographs of partial new materials can be downloaded from the supplementary PDF on the corresponding publication page of this paper on ResearchGate.

Abbreviations. TL, total length (in mm); Ch-L/W, length to width ratio of pedipalp chela; T-L/D, length to depth ratio of telson; PTC, pectinal tooth count; PVTC, pedipalp patella ventral trichobothrium count; PETC, pedipalp patella external trichobothrium count; FDC, pedipalp movable finger dentition count; IAD, inner accessory denticle; MD, median denticle; ID, inner denticle; OD, outer denticle; Eb_3 pos., relative position of trichobothrium Eb_3 on pedipalp chela manus (definition follows Kovařík et al., 2020: 8); P, pectine morphology (definition follows Kovařík et al., 2020: 21); MLMa, mediolateral major ocellus(i); PLMa, posterolateral major ocellus(i); PLMi, posterolateral minor ocellus(i); AC, anonymous collector.

Specimen Depositories. FKCP, personal collection of František Kovařík, Prague, Czech Republic (will in future be merged with the collections of the National Museum of Natural History, Prague, Czech Republic); VT, personal collection of Victoria Tang, Shanghai, China (will in future be donated to Natural History Museum, London, UK).

Systematics

Scorpiopidae Kraepelin, 1905

Scorpiops reini sp. n.

(Figures 1–72, 75, 111–112; Table 1)

<http://zoobank.org/lsid:zoobank.org:act:C3C4F41D-7A74-434F-868D-594296E9D2BA>

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. China, Yunnan, Dehong Prefecture, Yingjiang County, 24°35'27.0"N 97°41'34.0"E (24.590833°N 97.692778°E), 1362 m a. s. l.; VT & FKCP.

TYPE MATERIAL. China, Yunnan Province, Dehong Prefecture, Yingjiang County, 24°35'27.0"N 97°41'34.0"E (24.590833°N 97.692778°E), 1362 m a. s. l., 30 January 2024, 1♂ (holotype), 1♀ (paratype), 6 juvs. (paratype, FKCP), leg. unknown collector.

ETYMOLOGY. The specific epithet is a patronym in honor of Norwegian scorpologist Jan Ove Rein, who established the renowned website *The Scorpion Files* which has profoundly assisted numerous scorpion enthusiasts, including the author. Chinese equivalent: 瑞氏类蝎 (roughly as “Rein’s resemblant scorpion” in English; see Tang (2022a) for the rules of designation).

Figures 5–12: **Figures 5–8.** *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male, prosoma and mesosoma in dorsal (5–6) and ventral (7–8) views. **Figures 5, 7.** Under white light. **Figures 6, 8.** Under UV light. **Figures 9–12.** *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., paratype female, prosoma and mesosoma in dorsal (9–10) and ventral (11–12) views. **Figures 9, 11.** Under white light. **Figures 10, 12.** Under UV light. Scale bars = 5 mm.

DIAGNOSIS (♂♀). Total length (tergites contracted) ca. 55 mm for holotype male and ca. 48 mm for paratype female. Base color uniformly dark reddish black (appearing greyish black *in vivo* if not moistened); telson and ventral of prosoma and mesosoma reddish brown (*in vitro*). Cuticular surface matte and finely granular. Carapace with anteromedian notch subtriangular in male and dome-shaped in female; ocular tubercle distinct within ocular islet; ocular subislets relatively short and narrow (especially the anterocular subislet), moderately granular; interocular sulcus wide and distinct; superciliary carinae smooth to engraved; ocular sockets large. PTC 9–10 in male and 8 in female; pectines with marginal lamellae I and III present, marginal lamella II not delimited, but connected with middle lamella forming a single compact unit (P2); fulcra present; sternites III–VI lustrous, VII very weakly granular without distinct carinae. Pedipalp patella with strong prolateral apophysis; 17–19 external and 9–11 ventral trichobothria. Chela with 4 *V* series trichobothria; *Eb*₃ located in distal half of manus between *Dt* and *Est* (type A); Ch-L/W ca. 3.66 in male and ca. 3.19 in female. Dentate margin of movable fingers moderately undulate in male and weakly undulate in female, with 13 OD, 84–85 MD, 51–58 IAD and 6–7 ID. Telotarsi of leg I–VI with 5–8 stout median ventral spinules nearly in a single row with the terminal two always paired. Metasoma I–V with 10–8–8–8–7 carinae. Telson slender and relatively smooth; T-L/D ca. 3.32 in male and ca. 3.43 in female; annular ring developed.

DESCRIPTION (♂). All structures (except pedipalp movable fingers) were photographed under white light, with additional UV fluorescence imaging applied for prosoma, mesosoma, carapace, pectines, sternites and pedipalp chela. Description for the coloration is omitted as the specimens underwent decomposition.

Prosoma and mesosoma (Figs. 5–8, 13–18, 65–66). *Prosoma*: Carapace with pairs of MLMa, PLMa and PLMi, conforming to Type 3A lateral ocelli (Loria & Prendini, 2014); median ocular tubercle distinct within islet, elevated from antero- and postocular subislets; subislets relatively short, narrow and moderately granular, anterocular subislet shorter and less granular; interocular sulcus wide distinct; superciliary carinae smooth to engraved; ocular socket proportionally large. Dorsomedian part of the carapace (ca. 2/3 of total area) planar, with a heart-shaped region demarcated by coarse granules; lateral surfaces slanting downwards. Entire carapace densely covered with moderate granules, and adorned with lattice microstructures at non-granular regions; larger granules concentrated anteriorly at edges flanking anteromedian sulcus, and above and posterior to lateral ocelli; distinct carinae absent. Anterior margin of carapace with a prominent, subtriangular median notch leading to a wide, shallow, smooth anteromedian sulcus; circumocular and posteromedian sulci smooth; lateral surfaces with a pair of shallow central lateral sulci and prominent posterior lateral sulci, both non-granular; posterior marginal sulcus moderate. *Mesosoma*: All tergites moderately covered with small to moderate, pointed granules, becoming denser posteriorly; tergites III–VI with a relatively

weak median carina becoming progressively pronounced posteriorly, VII pentacarinata. Sternites III–IV lustrous, with several macrosetae arrayed along the posterior margin; sternite VII very weakly granular without distinct carinae; respiratory spiracles suboval. Genital operculum divided into two halves, with genital papillae at the base. Right pectine with 1st marginal lamella lineated from middle lamella but not forming a well-defined unit, 3rd marginal lamella only indicated; left pectine with 1st marginal lamella better defined, 2nd marginal lamella incompletely separated from middle lamella, 3rd marginal lamella only indicated; pectine teeth number 10/9; fulcra present and moderately developed (high width, low depth); several fluorescent microsetae present on the inner and outer margins of each pectine.

Metasoma and telson (Figs. 53–54, 67). Metasoma sparsely hirsute and granulated; carinae mostly formed by thin to rounded, discrete, small granules, except for the dorsosubmedian carinae on segments I–IV as well as the ventrolateral and ventromedian carinae on segment V, which are formed by more spiniform granules (serrated). Metasomal segment I with 10 carinae, II–IV with 8 carinae, and V with 7 carinae; intercarinal surfaces sparsely granular. Telson elongated and dorsally weakly concave; generally smooth with larger granules concentrated dorsolaterally; very sparsely hirsute; prominent annular ring developed. Vesicle with lateral surface furnished by one shallow longitudinal sulcus close to dorsal surface. Aculeus smooth, moderate in length and curvature.

Pedipalps (Figs. 25–30, 37–42, 49–50). Pedipalps very sparsely hirsute with mainly fluorescent microsetae, intercarinal surfaces scattered with small to moderate granules and patches of lattice microstructures. Patella with 17/19 external (5/5 *et*, 3/4 *est*, 3/3 *em*, 1/2 *esb*, 5/5 *eb*; homologous left trichobothria *est* and *esb* manifested as “petite” ones and were excluded) and 10/11 ventral trichobothria. Chela with 4 *V* series trichobothria; trichobothrium *Eb*₃ located in distal half of manus between *Dt* and *Est*. Femur with 5 complete, highly granular carinae; promedian carina slightly weaker, formed by more discrete granules, other 4 carinae formed by denser, coarser granules; retroventral carina incomplete, diffusing into random granules of the same size as adjacent intercarinal granules distally; dorsal surface coarsely granulated, ventral surface finely granulated. Patella with 5 granular carinae with finely and sparsely intercarinal surfaces; granules smaller on proventral carina; prolateral surface with two strong, triangular apophyses situated on the same vertical line, flanked by several much smaller spiniform granules; a reticulate pattern indicated on the ventral surface. Manus moderately adorned with small intercarinal granules on all surfaces, forming reticulate patterns; all carinae granular, formed by dense, rounded, moderate to large granules; subdigital and ventroexternal carinae obsolete; dorsal secondary, external secondary, ventrointernal, intermedian carinae partially incomplete, gradually diffusing to dispersed granules distally; dorsal marginal, digital and ventromedian carinae more complete with larger granules. Dentate margin of movable finger moderately undulate (proximal lobe present) with a corresponding notch on dentate margin of fixed finger;

Figures 13–18. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male, carapace (13, 16), pectines (14, 17) and sternites VI–VII (15, 18). **Figures 13–15.** Under white light (carapace show discoloration due to prolonged UV exposure, cf. Fig. 1). **Figures 16–18.** Under UV light. Scale bars = 5 mm (Fig. 13), 2 mm (Figs. 14–15).

Figures 19–24. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., paratype female, carapace (19, 22), pectines (20, 23) and sternites VI–VII (21, 24). **Figures 19–21.** Under white light. **Figures 22–24.** Under UV light. Scale bars = 5 mm (Fig. 19), 2 mm (Figs. 20–21).

Figures 25–36. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., pedipalp chela in dorsal (25, 28, 31, 34), external (26, 29, 32, 35) and ventral (27, 30, 33, 36) views. **Figures 25–30.** Holotype male, under white (25–27) and UV (28–30) light. **Figures 31–36.** Paratype female under white (31–33) and UV (34–36) light. Scale bars = 10 mm.

adorned by 13/13 OD, 84/85 MD, 55/51 IAD (same size as MD) and 6/6 ID; IAD series creates a second row along MD series without obvious subdivisions.

Legs (Figs. 57–60). Tibia and tarsomeres of legs with several macrosetae not arranged into bristle combs. Basitarsi of legs I–II with two rows of dense, thin, short spinules, but both absent on legs III–IV; a pair of pedal spurs present on the ventrodistal margins of all basitarsi. Telotarsi of legs I–IV with a row of stout, short ventromedian spinules (5–8 in number) of which two are always paired on the distal end. Ungues moderate in length, stout and curved. Carinae on femur and patella indicated by highly discrete granules.

Measurements. See Table 1.

SEXUAL DIMORPHISM. The female paratype (Figs. 3–4, 9–12, 19–24, 31–36, 43–48, 51–52, 55–56, 61–64, 68–70) yielded the following variations (left/right) in four meristics: (1) PTC 8/8; (2) PVTC 9/10; (3) PETC 18/17 external (5/5-4/3-3/3-1/1-5/5; homologous left trichobothrium *esb* replaced by a stout macroseta without peripherally elevated orifice, homologous right trichobothria *est* and *esb* absent); (4) FDC: 13/13-84/85-54/58-7/7, 7th left OD slightly integrated into the MD series. This single adult female examined here was smaller than the adult male, which is not considered as a sexual dimorphism since it is highly biased by the sample size (Yunnan *Scorpiops* species were often discovered with two size classes of adults). Another sexual dimorphism presented in the morphology of

Figures 37–48. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male (37–42) and paratype female (43–48), patella in dorsal (37, 43), external (38, 44) and ventral (39, 45) views, femur in dorsal (40, 46), external (41, 47) and ventral (42, 48) views, under white light. Scale bars = 10 mm.

Figures 49–52. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male (49–50) and paratype female (51–52), left (49, 51) and right (50, 52) movable fingers in dorsal view, under UV light. Scale bar = 3 mm.

pedipalp where the female had proportionally shorter femur, patella and chelal manus. Other external sexual dimorphisms conformed to those commonly observed in this genus: (1) genital papillae present in male and absent in female; (2) pectines relatively larger with longer pectinal tooth in male; (3) pedipalp movable finger with a weaker lobe in female.

AFFINITIES. The following interspecific differentiations of quantitative characters are based mostly on table 2 in Tang (2023: 18) and partially on the new materials examined. Newly examined *S. shidian* yielded the following PTC and PVTC variations (left/right): (1) male PTC: 7/7 ($n = 1$), 7/8 ($n = 1$), 8/8 ($n = 4$); (2) female PTC: 8/8 ($n = 1$); (3) male PVTC: 10/12 ($n = 1$), 11/11 ($n = 1$), 12/12 ($n = 3$), 13/12 ($n =$

1); (4) female PVTC: 12/12 ($n = 1$). Newly examined *S. xui* yielded the following PTC and PVTC variations (left/right): (1) male PTC: 7/7 ($n = 1$), 8/8 ($n = 1$); (2) female PTC: 7/6 ($n = 1$), 7/7 ($n = 2$); (3) male PVTC: 10/8 ($n = 1$), 10/10 ($n = 1$); (4) female PVTC: 10/9 ($n = 1$), 10/10 ($n = 2$). Two newly examined male *S. yangi* both yielded a PTC (left/right) of 7/7, as well as the following PVTC variations (left/right): 10/10 ($n = 1$) and 10/11 ($n = 1$).

Within Yunnan, *S. reini* sp. n. can be confidently distinguished from all of its congeneric geographic neighbors, namely *S. jendeki*, *S. shidian*, *S. tongtongi*, and *S. zhangshuyuani*. Its distinction from *S. jendeki* (cf. Tang et al., 2024) and *S. tongtongi* (cf. Tang, 2023) is quite obvious and hence omitted. The new species appears to be more akin

Figures 53–64. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male (53–54, 57–60) and paratype female (55–56, 61–64), under white light. **Figures 53–56.** Metasoma (twisted) in bilateral views; scale bar = 10 mm. **Figures 57–64.** Right legs I–IV in retrolateral view; scale bars = 5 mm.

to *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani* owing to their elongated pedipalps (cf. Figs. 71–75). However, the pedipalp chelae of those two species are nonetheless more slender (cf. Tang, 2023: figs. 109, 111, 133, 135), especially when comparing the adult males. Moreover, the proximal lobe on pedipalp movable finger is prominently stronger in *S. reini* sp. n. than the other two species (cf. Tang, 2023: figs. 110, 112, 134, 136). These two major distinctions also allow for the differentiation between *S. reini* sp. n. and a geographically more distant species, *S. xui* from Menglian County, Puer City (cf. Tang, 2023: figs. 125–128). Both *S. shidian* and *S. zhangshuyuani* also possess a slightly higher number of PVT (10–13 and 11–12, respectively) than the new species (10–11). The new species (9–10 in male and 8 in female) shares an overlapped PTC with *S. zhangshuyuani* (9 in male and 7–8 in females),

yet at least their females differ in the morphology of pectinal teeth (cf. Tang, 2022b: fig. 225). On the contrary, although the female PTCs are overlapped between *S. reini* sp. n. (8) and *S. shidian* (6–8), those of their males are completely separated (9–10 vs. 7–8 in *S. shidian*). Intraspecific variation of chelal and pectinal morphology in *S. shidian* can be inferred from Tang (2022b: figs. 122–129, 134–147).

Surprisingly, *S. reini* sp. n. bears a higher degree of resemblance to its geographically most distant congeners within Yunnan, *S. validus* from Honghe Prefecture and *S. yangi* from Wenshan Prefecture. All three species are characterized by the moderately elongated and relatively more robust chelae in both sexes. However, both sexes of *S. validus* possess a pair of evidently stronger finger lobe and notch than *S. reini* sp. n., especially when comparing the males (cf. Tang, 2023: figs.

Figures 65–70. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., holotype male (65–67) and paratype female (68–70), chelicerae in dorsal (65, 68) view, periocular morphosculpture of median ocelli (66, 69), telson in lateral view (67, 70), under white light. Scale bars = 1.5 mm (Figs. 65–66, 68–69), 3 mm (Figs. 67, 70).

Figures 71–75. Overall comparison within Yunnan congeners. **Figures 71–72.** *Scorpiops reini* sp. n., paratype female (71) and holotype male (72) *in vivo* habitus (photo: Tongtong). **Figures 73–74.** *Scorpiops shidian* (73, female; 74, male) *in vivo* habitus. **Figure 75.** Comparison between *Scorpiops yangi* (left), *S. validus* (middle) and *S. reini* sp. n. (right), females above, males below.

Figures 76–84. Comparative congeners. **Figures 76–79.** Pectines of *Scorpiops validus* (76–77) and *S. yangi* (78–79); female (76, 78) and males (78, 79). **Figures 80–84.** *Scorpiops beccaloniae*, holotype male, chela in dorsal (80) and external (81) views, movable finger in dorsal view (82), right pectine in ventral view (83), telson in lateral view (84), under white light (photo courtesy of F. Kovařík).

122, 124). Contrarily, *S. yangi* is distinguished by its relatively weak lobe in both sexes (cf. Tang, 2023: figs. 130, 132). When comparing their PTCs, both *S. validus* (6–8 in males and 6–7 in females) and *S. yangi* (6–7 in males and 5–6 in females) are well separated from *S. reini* sp. n. by their lower counts in both sexes. PVTc proved to be useless in differentiating these three species (*S. reini* sp. n.: 9–11; *S. validus*: 8–11; *S. yangi*: 9–11). Intraspecific variation of chelal and pectinal morphology in *S. validus* can be inferred from Tang (2022b: figs. 186–195, 201–210). Among adult males, *S. reini* sp. n. apparently represents the largest species of this genus known from Yunnan, although the holotype male was only slightly bigger than the largest male *S. validus* examined by the author. On the other hand, the paratype female was slightly smaller than the largest female *S. validus* examined by the author. However, both adults of *S. reini* sp. n. possessed notably more robust metasoma and larger telson than *S. validus* (Fig. 75). The relatively slenderer metasoma and telson are consistent among all examined *S. validus*.

Beyond Yunnan (also within the entire genus), *S. reini* sp. n. is most reminiscent of *S. beccaloniae* (Kovářik, 2005) from Mali Hka Valley (Kachin Hills, Myanmar), a species which we originally presumed to represent the type specimens (i.e., as a new record in China). This species was described based on a single adult male, characterized by a slightly lower PTC (8–9 vs. 9–10) and a slightly higher PVTc (12 vs. 10–11) than our new species. Those two values are not considered reliable given the fact that males of both species were based on a single specimen. Their meristics of PETC (18 vs. 17–19), OD (12–13 vs. 13) and IAD (50 vs. 51–58) are also close or overlapped. Although the counts of their ID (4 vs. 6–7) and MD (65 vs. 84–85) appear to differ more considerably, the differences are generally not significant enough to guarantee the interspecific distinction when referencing to the empirically observed intraspecific variation in Yunnan *Scorpiops* (cf. Tang, 2023: table 2). Nonetheless, their difference in the count of MD may still be relatively reliable, but more specimens are required to confirm its phenotypic stability. Both species fall into the type A position of trichobothrium Eb_3 (Kovářik et al., 2020: table 9); both species possess a pair of proportionally large median ocelli, a subtriangular carapacial anteromedian notch and a relatively robust metasoma (cf. Kovářik, 2005: fig. 13). The pectines were scored as type P4 (definition: 3 marginal and 1–5 middle lamellae) for *S. beccaloniae* in Kovářik et al. (2020: table 9). However, this character was deemed unstable by Tang (2022b: 34) given its presence of all four types in a single species, *S. shidian*. Likewise, the female paratype of our new species conformed to type P2 (definition: marginal lamellae I and III present, marginal lamella II not delimited, but connected with middle lamella forming a single compact unit), while the holotype male seemed to match both P2 and P3 (definition: two marginal and 1–4 middle lamellae); this is not regarded as a sexual dimorphism. In light of these, the differentiation between the males of the two species is mainly reliant upon their pedipalp chela morphology with the following distinctions proposed (cf. Figs. 80–81): (1) finger lobe and notch more

pronounced in *S. beccaloniae*; (2) chelal manus proportionally shorter with respect to its fixed finger in *S. beccaloniae*; (3) chelal manus proximally dilated (dorsointernal carina slanted inwards) in *S. beccaloniae*, while it is proximally narrowed (dorsointernal carina curved) in *S. reini* sp. n.; (4) chelal manus carinae composed of large, pointed, highly discrete granules in *S. beccaloniae*; whereas those granules are smaller and denser in *S. reini* sp. n. The fourth qualitative character (can be, for example, quantified by the number of granules present within a section of the carina with a cutoff boundary delimited by the condyle) is currently deemed as the most conspicuous and reliable distinction between the two species.

The validity of this new species against other known Yunnan congeners is supported genetically based on six offspring from the paratype female (unpublished). Due to practical constraints, these results, along with several other new discoveries, will be integrated into a more comprehensive review of this genus in China in a subsequent publication.

DISTRIBUTION. Known only from the type locality. This species is sympatric with *S. tongtongi* and *S. zhangshuyuani* according to the photographic records by the anonymous collector, which is also confirmed by the recorded localities of those species (Fig. 130). The discovery of the new species has rendered Yingjiang County (as well as Dehong Prefecture) the most speciose region for *Scorpiops*.

Periocular morphology of median ocelli

The varying morphologies of the “median ocular tubercle” (MOT) among distinct *Scorpiops* species from Yunnan were first indicated in Tang (2022b: 3, 14), leveraged as a crucial character to distinguish *S. tongtongi* from all other medium to large-sized Yunnan congeners (i.e., excluding *S. jendeki*; cf. Tang, 2022b: figs. 33–39): “...small median ocular tubercle and short superciliary carinae...”. Tang (2023: 21, 46) further discussed this character in detail and incorporated it into the first group of diagnostic characters in a dichotomous key for differentiating Yunnan *Scorpiops* (Tang, 2023: 49). The terminology was updated to “median ocular coverage”, emphasizing its relative size and shape. In Tang (2023: table 3), this character was binarized, with one being short and oval, and the other being elongated and rhomboid. *Scorpiops jendeki* and *S. tongtongi* fall into the first category, while all other Yunnan congeners fall into the second. Subsequently, Tang et al. (2024: 3–5) introduced a new set of terminologies in order to describe the periocular morphology of median ocelli in a more meticulous manner. The term “ocular tubercle” was restricted to a rounded area that encloses the two median ocelli, albeit without definitive boundaries. The entire “ocular tubercle coverage” was replaced by the term “ocular islet (OI)”, which was further divided into an “anterocular subislet (AOSI)” and a “postocular subislet (POSI)” by the MOT *sensu stricto*. Four preliminary types were proposed, with Type 1 corresponding to those observed in *S. jendeki* and *S. tongtongi*, and Type 3 to those observed in other Yunnan *Scorpiops*. The observed

Figures 85–126. Median ocelli of *Scorpiops reini* sp. n. (111–112), *S. jendeki* (85–86, 105–106), *S. lowei* (87–88, 107–108), *S. puerensis* (89–90, 109–110), *S. shidian* (91–92, 113–114), *S. tongtongi* (93–94, 115–116), *S. vachoni* (95–96, 117–118), *S. validus* (97–98, 119–120), *S. xui* (99–100, 121–122), *S. yangi* (101–102, 123–124) and *S. zhangshuyuani* (103–104, 125–126). **Figures 85–104.** In dorsal view. **Figures 105–126.** In lateral view (left side).

Figure 127. Map showing the known distribution of all Yunnan *Scorpiops* species, coordinates taken from past papers, examined localities, and (selectively) iNaturalist. *Scorpiops reini* sp. n. (☆); *S. jendeki* (●); *S. lowei* (●); *S. puerensis* (●); *S. shidian* (●); *S. tongtongi* (●); *S. vachoni* (●); *S. validus* (●); *S. xui* (●); *S. yangi* (●); *S. zhangshuyuani* (●); including *S. cf. zhangshuyuani* from Lincang City, to be detailed in a subsequent study); *S. sp.* (aff. *vachoni*; ●). The type locality of *S. beccaloniae* is indicated by a cross, approximated from Kovářik et al. (2020: fig. 799).

rhomboid shape in the Yunnan *Scorpiops* conforming to Type 3 ocular islet was due to their two larger subislets that resemble a pair of opposing triangles, both tapering to the extremities. This rhomboid profile is more evident under UV illumination (cf. Tang et al., 2024: figs. 3–4) owing to the more brightly fluorescent circumocular sulcus (COS).

Tang et al. (2024: 3–4) defined those types using a few descriptors, including two features: (1) the distinctiveness of MOT within OI; (2) the elevation of AOSI and POSI. In fact, according to Tang et al. (2024), feature 1 is dependent of feature 2 where planar subislets naturally contrast with the raised MOT. However, MOT is not separated from the two

subislets by any definitive boundaries (e.g., a sulcus). Instead, MOT is identified optically, as the superciliary carinae (SCC) are at least partially lustrous. The reduction of large, lustrous granules on the relatively matte subislets, along with the weak or absent interocular sulcus (IOS) in Type 1, makes MOT quite distinctive due to its reflective properties. On the contrary, Type 3 typically features multiple smooth, black granules on the subislets that result in their texture reminiscent of MOT. In addition, their SCC may be engraved or granular and are separated by a distinct IOS, which together disintegrate the shiny surface and render MOT less distinct compared to the subislets. This combination of surface morphosculptures elongates the reflective area, thereby leading to the “rhomboid” appearance of the entire structure.

The present study critically revises these two features. First, it warrants clarification that qualitative descriptors like “oval” and “rhomboid” are not always well-demarcated in terms of their definitions. The OI is confined by the COS, which is universally fusiform across all *Scorpiops* species and largely dictates the profile of OI (Figs. 85–104). What led to the ostensibly “oval” and “rhomboid” appearance? We propose that this was a result of dual factors, due to the profiles of both subislets themselves and their peripheral COS. If the subislets are relatively wide, the entire structure would appear “rhomboid”. This superficial geometry is further enhanced by a deeper and narrower COS. Conversely, narrow subislets and a shallower and wider COS would render an “oval” profile, primarily shaped by the rounded MOT.

This brings us to the topic of subislet elevation. To verify this claim, the current author investigated the MOT of all Yunnan *Scorpiops* from the lateral side (Figs. 105–126). It was revealed that all species exhibited a hill-shaped OI with a similar elevation, although the uneven carapacial surface in *Scorpiops* obstructs a clear view into the surrounding landscape of MOT from the lateral view. Contrary to what one would expect for a rounded bump, an abrupt anterior and/or posterior descent was not always observed in or exclusive to *S. jendeki* or *S. tongtongi*. The MOT of both species gradually declined into the subislets. All Yunnan *Scorpiops*, except for *S. jendeki* and *S. tongtongi*, fall into Type 3 OI, which often shows large, rhomboid, and well-delineated OI. The cause may be binary: (1) subislets are indeed typically more elevated in Type 3 OI, but only to a limited extent; (2) COS is also typically deeper in Type 3 OI. As clarified earlier, the deeper COS in most Yunnan *Scorpiops* contributed to their more elevated and well-defined appearance. These features are more apparent when examining the carapace under UV illumination (cf. Tang, 2023: figs. 137–154). As additional information, photographs taken in the front view for some newly examined Yunnan *Scorpiops* can be found in the supplementary file on ResearchGate.

Consequently, as an amendment to the proposals in Tang et al. (2024), we suggest placing less emphasis on the elevation of the subislets. Furthermore, regarding the shape or distinctiveness of MOT, we suggest this is essentially the same as the presence or absence of IOS and subislet granules, as aforementioned. Therefore, it is more recommendable to concentrate on the morphosculptures of OI. Although

the periocular morphology of *Scorpiops* species requires further examination on a broader scale to define the potential types and the specific species categorized under each type need confirmation, we argue that the utility of the relevant terminologies remains valid and can still be used for the ordinary taxonomic descriptions.

It was also noticed that in our new species, *S. reini* sp. n., the MOT is quite large relative to the maximum width of either subislet (Figs. 66, 69), which puts it closer to the Type 1 OI. From another perspective, the subislets are rather narrow and less developed. Moreover, the large ocular sockets resemble those in many congeners provisionally categorized under Type 4 OI. However, the engraved SCC, distinct IOS, and coarsely granulated POSI prompted us to describe its characters as per Type 3 OI. In any case, the periocular morphology in genus *Scorpiops* is largely understudied. We expect more revisions for the four preliminary categories.

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